

CLINICAL AND LABORATORY CHARACTERISTICS, DIAGNOSIS OF PYELONEPHRITIS IN CHILDREN UNDER COVID-19 PANDEMIC CONDITIONS

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Abstract: Pyelonephritis remains a disease of particular medical, social and economic importance. At the turn of 2019-2020, humanity was affected by a new viral infection, SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19), which spread rapidly in many countries and reached pandemic proportions. It was found that 27.06% of hospitalised patients with coronavirus infection had kidney damage.

Key words: SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19), pyelonephritis, children

Objective of the study: Determination of clinical and laboratory features, early diagnosis of pyelonephritis in children

Subject and object of study: 50 patients with pyelonephritis, aged 2 to 15 years, in contact with COVID-19 were recruited. Fifty children with pyelonephritis not infected with COVID-19 disease were taken as control group.

Materials and Methods:

1. General clinical - history, pedigree analysis, examination, blood and urine tests.

2. instrumental - renal ultrasound with Dopplerometry, blood pressure measurement.

RESULTS: As shown by our investigations, general intoxication syndrome - 43 (86%), dysuria - 33 (66%), pain syndrome - 17 (34%), temperature reaction - 48 (96%) children. Clinical manifestations of pyelonephritis in the second group were temperature reactions in 22 (44%) children, signs of intoxication in 18 (36%), pain syndromes in 11 (22%), dysuric syndromes in 7 (14%) children.

Leukocyturia was detected in 43 (86%) children of the first group. Proteinuria from 0,03 to 2,72 g/l was revealed in the majority of patients - 46 (92%) from the first group and to a lesser degree in 20 (40%) from the second group ($p < 0,05$).

Conclusions: Pyelonephritis in children exposed to COVID-19 was characterized by predominant signs of intoxication. A recurrent course of chronic pyelonephritis was observed.

